
CAPITAL ASSET PRICING MODEL AND STOCK INVESTMENT DECISION OF COMMERCIAL BANKS IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the impact of the capital asset pricing model and stock investment decision of commercial banks in Nigeria, with a focus on the influence of risk-free rate, beta coefficient, and market return on market capitalization. Utilizing an ex-post facto research design, secondary data from 2019 to 2023 was sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin. Panel data analysis, including descriptive analysis and pooled regression models, was employed to analyze market return (ROTM), beta, and risk-free rate as proxies for CAPM, while market capitalization was used as a proxy for commercial bank stock performance. The findings reveal a significant and positive relationship between market return and market capitalization, indicating that favorable market conditions drive higher stock valuations in the banking sector. In contrast, the risk-free rate and beta coefficient show negative but statistically insignificant relationships with market capitalization, suggesting that interest rates and systematic risk have minimal influence on stock valuation. The study concludes that market returns are the primary determinant of market capitalization in Nigeria's banking sector, with investors prioritizing overall market performance over interest rates and risk when making investment decisions. The study recommends that Nigerian banks should monitor market trends to attract investments, manage interest rate fluctuations and systematic risk through effective risk management, and enhance investor confidence by improving transparency and communication on market performance.

Keywords: Capital Asset Pricing Model, Market capitalization, Risk free rate, Beta coefficient and return on market

INTRODUCTION

Among Challenges of investors in the investment world is the problem of investment choices that suit their individual's risk profile and financial goals. In an ever-changing global context, investors are faced with a variety of complex and often confusing investment choices. From stocks, bonds and mutual funds to alternative investments such as real estate and cryptocurrencies, each investment instrument has its own characteristics and risks (Abidin, Ciptaning & Syadiah, 2024). Sometimes investors have difficulty to determine which stocks is worthy to buy (Wijaya & Ferrari, 2020).

Investment involves the process of putting money into Ventures such as stocks, bonds or real estate. It is a commitment to allocate a certain amount of funds owned by an individual or a corporate organization to one or more assets which is expected to be able to provide returns in the future. Investment is one of the most important channels of increasing an individual's or corporate organization's ability to accumulate and maintain wealth. The main goals of investment include safety, Income and growth of capital. (Adams, 2023). In this challenging era, there is no doubt that investment plays an important role in securing our financial future. Whether to prepare for retirement, create long-term wealth, or achieve other financial goals, investment provides a powerful tool for achieving our financial dreams. (Abidin et al 2024). Investment as an activity is classified into two forms, investment in real asset and investment in financial asset. Real asset investment has to do with commitment of financial stake in the form of physical tangible asset, while investments in financial assets are investments in the form of securities which is conducted in the money market and capital market. The form of financial investments in the money market can be described as certificates of deposit and money market securities which are short-term in nature while financial asset investments in the capital market which are long term in nature can be in the form of bonds, warrants, mutual funds, options, futures, and stocks (Yulianti, 2014; Wijaya & Ferrari, 2020).

One of the most popular securities instruments in capital market is stocks. Investing in stocks is indeed a big long-term profit field (Sari, Atmadjaja & Ferawati 2022.). However, Investment be it in stock or any other form is not just an activity that take place just that way. It is a risk-filled action. Investors need a deep understanding of financial markets, risk analysis, and the selection of investment instruments that suit their individual's risk profile and financial goals. In addition, an investor carrying out investment activity requires patience, discipline and the right strategy to manage an investment portfolio well. Investors in the investment world must be able to see promising investment opportunities so that they can generate an ideal rate of return with minimal risk (Rosyita and Heikal, 2023). An investor's accuracy in finding information and processing information is very necessary because it will be used as a decision-making tool for investing that will determine how much profit will be gained in the future (Putra, 2013; Wijaya and Ferrari, 2020). Rapidly growing investment is not released from risk, therefore potential investor should be capable of their insight, explore information or see investments that will be profitable in the future. Investors sometimes get difficulty in determining which stocks will produce a large return with a small risk (Wijaya et al., 2020). An investor must be able to estimate the return of an individual security. Thus, accurate stock valuation is critical for every investors, managers, analysts, and researchers. It entails putting in efforts to appraise businesses and identify undervalued stocks for investment. Thus, it is important for an investor to understand the rudiments of investment, its underlying concepts, also they will also be in need of analytical tools that can help them make smart investment decisions and chose accurate level of risk while investing in the future. To achieve this, a balance market model such as Capital Asset pricing model will be

required. These models which are mathematical representation of the behavior of financial markets, aiming to predict future prices, returns, or risk help investors, analysts, and researchers understand market dynamics, make informed decisions, and manage risk. The CAPM describes the relationship between investment risk and return. It is one of the most important theories in modern finance, a methodology that may be used to determine the risk and rate of return of a financial asset. The CAPM was developed to aid investors in making stock selection decisions and decreasing the risk of their investments. The capital asset pricing model (CAPM) considers an asset's sensitivity to systematic or market risk, which is commonly represented in the stock market by the beta value. (Mulyaningsih and Heikal,2022). CAPM can assist investors in comprehending difficult market situations, avoiding investment risk, and calculating the amount of return they will receive. (Hasan, 2019; Mulyaningsih and Jerry Heikal 2022).

The Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) was pioneered by Willian Sharpe, John Litner, and Jan Mossin in 1964-1966 postulates that expected return on an asset above the risk free rate is directly proportional to a non - diversifiable risk, i.e., a linear relationship exists between a residual risk and the value of an asset. The CAPM was developed as a model for investment appraisal, share valuation, and for pricing individual's securities or portfolio. (Afolabi, Njogo, Areghan, Olugbenle and Olusesi 2017). CAPM drawn from the modern portfolio theory came into existence on how systematic risk can be measured. (Afolabi et al, 2017). The core of the CAPM model is represented by the beta coefficient which measures the sensitivity of the financial instrument in relation to the systematic risk. CAPM can assist investors in determining the risk of a portfolio that cannot be diversified and comparing it with the predicted rate of return. (Rosyita and Heikal 2023).CAPM is a balance model in which the expected level of profit (return) from investing in securities is determined by the amount of systematic risk (beta) multiplied by the risk premium plus the risk-free rate of return. (Abidin , Ciptaning ,and Syadiah 2024).No investor go into investment activity be it in stock or any other venture without accurate stock valuation which will need the help of a balance model. The importance of capital asset pricing model as an efficient valuation tool in stock investment decision making has been labelled to be crucial in the investment arena. It is expected that the CAPM helps investors describe complex market conditions, reduce investment risk, and estimate the amount of return earned. CAPM also aims to assist investors in making stock selections and minimizing risky investments. In addition, CAPM can assist investors in determining the risk of a portfolio that cannot be diversified and comparing it with the predicted rate of return. In addition to its frequent use in portfolio analysis and investment decision-making, CAPM is particularly useful in assessing investment returns and risk. Some of the main functions of the Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) are very important in the financial world, especially in investment analysis and portfolio management. Although the CAPM has some real-world drawbacks, such as simplistic assumptions and no transaction costs, it remains an important tool in financial analysis and investment decision-making. This study tends to evaluate the impact of capital asset pricing model in stock investment decision making in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Capital asset pricing model as an efficient valuation tool in stock investment decision making is crucial in the investment world. Despite its importance as a financial asset pricing tool, its validity has been questioned .Numerous studies have investigated the applicability and validity of CAPM as a model for investment appraisal, share valuation, and for pricing individual's securities or portfolio. While some authors hold a negative view, others has continued to uphold a positive view about its subject matter. This positive view is

traditionally popularised by William Sharpe (1964) Capital Asset Prices: A Theory of Market Equilibrium under Conditions of Risk .Although subsequent supporters of this development hypothesis are many but opinions as to the relative magnitudes of the validity and applicability of CAPM as a balanced market model in stock investment decision making vary markedly among authors (see Douglas,(2024, Negara,2023, Haq , Sukono, and Saputra J., 2024, Laili , Devina, Tsabita, & Pandin, 2024, Beby, Nisrul and Mawarni,2022, Sri and Doni, 2024, Sri and Jerry, 2022, Do, 2014, Sustari, Nur and Fahman 2022). Not much have been done on the different aspects of capital asset pricing model and stock investment decision making. Some of these areas include Quantifying Risk in Investment Decision-Making (Jaheera, Sunitha, Regina, Ravi and Satyanarayana, 2024), Analysis of the Accuracy Level of the Balance Model in Stock Investment Prediction in the LQ45 Index (Afifah & Maretha, 2024), Optimal Selection of Stock Portfolios Using Multi-Criteria Decision-Making Methods (Jing, Imeni, Edalatpanah, Alburaihan, Khalifa, 2023). The researcher has so far seen few Nigerian studies on all-inclusive capital Asset pricing model and stock investment decision making in the Nigeria context. This is no known study that has taken the various dimensions of capital Asset pricing model in relation to stock investments in Nigeria. This is the motivation for this study.

This study is therefore apt because of the scope as Well as the geographical gap that has been identified from previous studies on this subject matter. Capital asset pricing model has been labeled as an efficient valuation tool in stock investment decision making in the investment arena. As a balance market model, it is expected that the CAPM helps investors describe complex market conditions, reduce investment risk, and estimate the amount of return earned. CAPM also aims to assist investors in making stock selections and minimizing risky investments. However, the extent to which its various units contribute to stock investment decision making is yet to be empirically determined especially in the Nigerian context. This is the Prompting of this study, namely to examine the impact of Capital asset Pricing model on Stock Investment decision making in commercial banks in Nigeria.

Aims and Objectives of the Study

The main aim of this study is to investigate the impact of capital asset pricing model and stock investment decision making in commercial banks in Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives of this study are to determine the Impact of;

1. Risk free rate on market capitalization in Nigeria
2. Beta coefficient on market capitalization in Nigeria
3. Return of the market on market capitalization in Nigeria.

Research Hypotheses

To achieve the objectives of the study and answer the research questions, the following null hypotheses are postulated for testing.

1. Risk free rate (Rf) has no significant impact on market capitalization in Nigeria
2. Beta coefficient has no significant impact on market capitalization in Nigeria.
3. Return of the market has no significant impact on market capitalization in Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Framework

Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH)

The Efficient-market hypothesis was developed by Eugene Fama in 1965. Efficient Market state that all important information stocks is reflected in the stock price (Eugene F, 2017; Wijaya and Ferrari, 2020). i.e financial markets reflect all available information, making it for impossible for investors to consistently achieve returns in excess of the market's average.

i.e. the financial markets are efficient, so no one can gain an edge in them. In 1970, Fama wrote another paper that explored the idea of market efficiency in more depth, noting that it seemed to take three forms as follows:

Weak-form efficiency: Suggests that all past information is priced into securities. Fundamental analysis of securities can provide an investor with information to produce returns above market averages in the short term but there are no "patterns" that exist. Therefore, fundamental analysis does not provide long-term advantage and technical analysis will not work (Bodie and Marcus, 2018; Wijaya and Ferrari, 2020). In this form, market prices reflect all past trading information, such as historical prices and trading volumes. According to weak-form efficiency, technical analysis (the study of past price and volume data) cannot consistently generate excess returns because this information is already reflected in stock prices.

Semi-strong-form efficiency: This implies that all publicly available information, including news and past trading data, is fully reflected in stock prices. As a result, neither technical analysis nor fundamental analysis (the study of financial statements and economic factors) can consistently beat the market, because all available information is already incorporated into prices. Neither fundamental analysis nor technical analysis can provide an advantage for an investor and that new information is instantly priced in to securities (Bodie and Marcus, 2018; Wijaya and Ferrari, 2020).

Strong-form efficiency: This is referred to as the most robust version of the efficient-market hypothesis. This hypothesis contends that all information, public and private, is fully reflected in stock prices. In other words, no individual or group of investors possesses information that can consistently yield superior returns. This form of efficiency suggests that insider trading is futile in the long run, as insider information is also reflected in stock prices. Strong Form EMH does not say some investors or money managers are incapable of capturing abnormally high returns but that there are always outliers included in the averages (Bodie and Marcus, 2018; Wijaya and Ferrari, 2020).

2.2 Conceptual review

2.2.1 Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM)

Based on asset portfolio theory, the Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) is a theory established by the famous American economists William Sharpe, John Lintner, Jack Treynor, and Jan Mossin. In this theory, the relationship between asset returns and risk is fully reflected by a simple model, which is a breakthrough in modern finance. The core theory of CAPM is that in a competitive equilibrium capital market, only undiversifiable systematic risk (usually measured by the β coefficient) can have an impact on expected returns by eliminating unsystematic risk through diversification. In other words, the β coefficient linearity is correlated with expected returns. (Jianing, 2022). The CAPM model is a balancing model that depicts a more straightforward risk and returns relationship and only employs one variable (also known as a beta variable) to characterize risk. (Tandelilin 2010; Beby, Nisrul, and Mawarni, 2022). According to the CAPM model, the greater the beta coefficient gained from stock, the higher the rate of return and risks that investors will receive. The rate of return of a market may be used to represent the degree of expected return, risk-free return, and regular or beta hazards in the CAPM model (Kholishoh, et al 2018; Beby, Nisrul, and Mawarni, 2022).

The Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) is a financial model used to calculate the expected rate of return of an investment based on the level of systematic risk or market risk. The model

helps investors and financial analysts in assessing whether the investment is profitable enough considering the risks involved. In the CAPM, the expected rate of return of an investment (also known as the expected rate of return or the required rate of return) can be calculated using the following formula:

$$R_s = R_f + \beta_i(R_m - R_f)$$

Where:

R_s : expected rate of return on a particular investment

R_f : risk-free rate of return, such as the interest rate on government bonds

β_i : beta coefficient, which measures the sensitivity of an investment to changes in the overall market

R_m : overall market rate of return

The capital; Asset pricing model can be used with the following assumptions;

1. Every investor is a rational investor and a risk taker. They buy and sell securities at competitive prices
2. There are no transaction costs or taxes. They lend and borrow at the risk free rate.
3. Investors have homogeneous expectations, having access to publicly available information thus risks and returns are similar without no privileges.
4. Investors only hold efficient portfolio or securities. No investor would want to hold an inefficient portfolio if he has all the available information about the market.
5. Investors have the same time horizon.
6. Only systematic risk affects a security rate of return.

The risk free rate (R_f)

The risk free rate of return is the minimum expected return of an investment. It is the rate of return an investor earn whether he invest in a risk-less or risky investment. The concept of the risk free rate is the fact that there is default. Irrespective of the riskiness of any asset, the risk free rate must be achieved. (Gbalam, 2024)

The 'risk-free rate' in the CAPM, which assumes that investors in the market can borrow at a rate without restriction, is obviously not possible in Nigeria's financial markets. The risk-free interest rate is based on the interest rate of treasury bills. The short investment time and the guarantee of the state's creditworthiness of treasury bills allow them to be generally considered an asset without both the credit risk and the interest rate risk. However, with the continuous development of Nigeria's economy, inflation is becoming more and more serious, along with the increasing purchasing power risk. Once there is inflation, there is no risk-free asset or risk-free interest rate (Jianing, 2022).

Risk Free Return

Risk-free return is a concept used in the world of finance to measure the performance of an investment or investment portfolio by taking into account the level of risk involved. It refers to the expected rate of return of an investment if there were no risks associated with it. In practice, risk-free returns are often calculated by referring to the rate of return on financial instruments that are considered risk-free, such as government bonds that are considered very safe. Examples are the interest rate on government bonds (T-Bill) or the interest rate on stable bank deposits. Risk-free returns are an important reference in portfolio analysis and investment decision making. Investors often compare the actual return of an investment with the risk-free return to evaluate whether they are earning a return large enough to offset the risk they are taking. (Abidin, Ciptaning & Syadiah, 2024).

Expected Rate of Return (E(RI))

Expected Rate of Return is the expected profit or anticipated from something investment or project. These are estimates or projections based on analysis of historical data, the risks involved, and other factors that may affect investment results. The expected rate of return can be calculated using a variety of methods, including fundamental analysis, technical analysis, or complex financial models. It helps investors in making investment decisions by taking into account the potential profits and risks involved. Factors that influence the expected Rate of Return include current market conditions, overall economic conditions, interest rates, regulatory changes, and other factors that may affect investment performance. Expected Rates of Return are estimates only and do not guarantee actual results. Investing always involves risk, and actual results may differ from expectations. (Abidin, et al., 2024). There are risk free assets also referred to as risk less assets and risky assets. The riskier an asset, the higher the expected rate of return. For an additional risk an investor embark upon. This additional return earned by an investor as a result of taking an additional unit of risk is called risk premium which is expected return minus the risk free rate ($R_s - R_f$). Therefore, investors should conduct careful analysis and consider all relevant factors before making an investment decision based on his preference and risk appetite.

Individual Stock Rates of Return

An individual stock's rate of return refers to the rate of profit or loss earned from investing in a particular stock over a certain period of time. This can be calculated by comparing the purchase price and sale price of shares, as well as taking advantage of the dividends paid by the company. The rate of return on an individual stock can vary significantly depending on the company's performance, market conditions, and other factors that influence stock prices.

Individual stock returns can also be influenced by internal company factors such as financial performance, company management, and product innovation. Investors often use individual stock returns as a metric to assess their investment performance. By monitoring individual stock returns, investors can evaluate whether an investment is successful or not, and make investment decisions based on that information (Abidin, et al., 2024).

Market Return

This is the average expected return of all the assets in the market. The allocation line of an investment is the combination of an investment portfolio which guarantees an optimal return at a particular level of risk or lowest risk at a particular rate of return. The total return of an investment portfolio is the summation of the risk-free rate of return & risk premium ($R_f + (R_m - R_f)$).

A. Systematic Risk of Individual Stocks /The Beta Coefficient

Systematic risk also referred to as the market risk or undiversifiable risk in the context of individual stocks refers to risk that cannot be avoided or eliminated even with good portfolio diversification. This is different from specific or diversifiable risk, which is the risk that is specific to a particular stock and can be reduced through diversification. The Systematic or market risk is measured by the Beta coefficient (β). Systematic risk cannot be diversified and eliminated and need to be compensated. The investor is keenly interested in the risk that cannot be diversify by him rather than concentrating on the total risk of an investment, an investor is bothered about the market risk (micro economic dynamics) and see how they can insulate their investments in such a way that the investor will not affected by these micro economic dynamics .This is the essence of the Beta coefficient. Beta (β) is a measure of a stock's volatility in relation to the overall market. It's used in the Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) to assess the risk associated with a particular investment.

Measures of Stock Investment Decision

Market Capitalization

One form of ownership that one can have in a company is shares, also known as equity or capital stock. Owning a share indicates that one owns a small part of the company, which is shown in the form of an electronic certificate or share sheet. A stock exchange is a place where stocks can be traded. In Nigeria Well-known stock exchanges is the Nigeria Exchange group (NGX). In the secondary market, investors can buy and sell stocks through stockbrokers or online trading platforms. Whether planning for retirement or diversifying an investment portfolio, investing in stocks can be an important component of one's financial strategy. However, it is important to remember that investing in stocks also involves risk and stock prices can change. One should do research and understand the stock market before investing in stocks. Rosyita and Heikal, (2023)

2.3 Empirical review

Beby, Nisrul, and Mawarni, (2022) Using the Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) technique, evaluate stock investment decision-making in the tourist industry listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange between 2018 and 2021. The findings acquired are stock investment decisions in the tourist industry listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange using the Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) approach. Stock investment decisions cannot be made because tourist industry listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange have inefficient shares. Since the Ci calculation's result does not exceed the cutoff threshold value. This is reflected in the stock's projected return ($0.00264561 < 0.00288417$), which is lower than the market's expected return.

Sri and Doni, (2024) examine various stock investments of all companies listing in Jakarta Islamic Index using the Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) method, to help investors pick efficient and inefficient stock. The sampling technique used was purposive sampling method and acquired 16 stocks. The results show that there was positive relationship or non linear relationship between systematic risk and expected return. There are 13 stocks included on efficient and investment decisions should be taken by investors was to buy efficient stocks, while there are 3 stocks included on inefficient and investment decisions should be taken by investors was to sell inefficient stocks.

Hasmalini and Heikal, (2023) investigate the impact of feasibility level of investment in BEI index shares for the 2023 period using the Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) method in determining investment decisions. Using descriptive quantitative research, the population of this research is financial sector companies, Distribution which are listed on the index IDX Industrial Classification or IDX-IC for the period November 2022 – October 2023. The researcher used 10 shares of financial holdings industry companies determined by the researcher. This researcher used Microsoft Excel linear regression data analysis to determine the beta coefficient of the Capital Asset Pricing Modeling (CAPM) method and compares the expected return with the stock market rate of return during the observation period to better differentiate between efficient and inefficient stocks. The results show that eight (8) companies have efficient shares and two (2) companies have inefficient shares which can be seen on the SML Security Market Line (SML) graph or CAPM model securities market line (GPS) for efficient shares and inefficient shares.

Rosyita and Heikal, (2023) investigate the application of the capital asset pricing model (Capm) Method as a basis for decision making to invest in shares in the road transportation sector to determine the types of stocks that are undervalued and overvalued based on stock returns and risks when making stock investment decisions. The study analyzes the shares of

companies in the road transportation sector listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) for the period November 2022 to October 2023. The study took seven (7) company stocks as samples. The results show that the seven (7) company stocks fall into the undervalued category because their individual stock returns are greater than the expected rate of return, and none of the stocks fall into the overvalued or inefficient category.

Afolabi, Njogo, Areghan, Olugbenle & Olusesi, (2017) examined the effect of capital asset pricing model (CAPM) for the Nigerian stock exchange using monthly stock values of 20 listed firms for the period of ten years (January 2006-December 2015) covering the periods and the aftermath of the 2008/2009 global economic crisis. In order to enhance the precision of the beta estimates and reduce the statistical problems that arise from measurement errors in individual beta estimates, the securities were combined into portfolios. The study employed simple ordinary least square (OLS) regression technique and found no conclusive evidence for the application of capital asset pricing model (CAPM) in the Nigerian Stock Exchange.

METHODOLOGY

The study employs the ex-post facto research design. The data for the study was sourced through secondary data obtained from Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin from 2019 - 2023. The data was generated from five commercial banks. The capital asset pricing model is proxy of risk free rate, beta coefficient and market return while stock investment decision making is used to measure market capitalization proxy of commercial banks. The study uses Descriptive analysis and Panel data. The estimation will be done using E-view 10.0 software and the result will be interpreted based on the established criteria at the chosen level of significance.

Model Specification

This study specifies the relationship between the dependent variable (market capitalization) and the proxies of the independent variable (capital asset pricing Model-Risk free rate, Beta and market return) in the following functional relationship.

The mathematical function is transferred into the following econometric model:

$$MCAP = \beta_0 + \text{LOGROT}M_{it} + \text{LOGBCOE}F_{it} + \text{LOGROT}M_{it} + u_{it} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where Y_t = Dependent Variable of bank for time period t ;

α_0 = Constant;

β_1 = Coefficient of explanatory variables;

X_{it} = Explanatory variables of bank for time period t ; and

ϵ_{it} = Error term of commercial bank for time period t .

From equation 1 above, the following models were developed:

$$Y_{it} = f(MCAP) \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

$$X_{it} = f(\text{LOGRFR}, \text{LOGBCOE}F, \text{LOGROT}M) \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

Substituting models 2 and 3 into model 1, the following model is formulated.

$$\text{LOGMCAP} = \alpha_0 + \text{LOGRFR}_{it} + \text{LOGBCOE}F_{it} + \text{LOGROT}M_{it} + u_{it} \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

Where;

LOGMCAP = Market Capitalization

LOGRFR = risk free rate

LOGBCOE F = Beta

LOGROT M = market return

Where;

B = parameters to be estimated

B₀ = intercept constant

B1..... β_3 = coefficients (estimate/slope) of the explanatory variables

Table 1: Data of Capital Asset Pricing Model and Stock Investment of Commercial Banks in Nigeria

YEAR	COY	S/N	Return of the Market	BETA Coefficient	Risk-Free-Rate	Market CAP
2019	GTBank	1	511,842,259	1.2	10%	123,471,114
2020		1	578,576,776	1.15	10%	123,471,114
2021		1	473,707,243	1.1	12%	123,471,114
2022		1	405,608,348	1.05	11%	123,471,114
2023		1	359,912,076	1.00	9%	123,471,114
2019	WEMA Bank	2	55,356,851	1.05	10%	8,698,230
2020		2	59,352,833	1.08	11%	8,698,230
2021		2	1,153,076,746	1.1	12%	8,698,230
2022		2	968,582,084	1.12	11%	8,698,230
2023		2	62,872,234	1.15	10%	8,698,230
2019	UBA	3	501,601	1.00	9%	115,815
2020		3	477,940	0.95	10%	115,815
2021		3	446,522	1.05	10%	115,815
2022		3	364,598	1.1	11%	115,815
2023		3	400,860	1.15	12%	115,815
2019	FBN	4	6,203,526	1.1	11%	233,392
2020		4	7,689,028	1.12	10%	233,392
2021		4	8,932,373	1.15	12%	233,392
2022		4	16,937,684	1.2	11%	233,392
2023		4	10,577,710	1.25	12%	233,392
2019	ACCESS BANK	5	539,488	1.1	9%	251,811
2020		5	653,896	1.05	10%	251,811
2021		5	871,450	1.1	11%	251,811
2022		5	1,068,665	1.2	10%	251,810
2023		5	440,800	1.15	11%	212,439

Source: Annual Financial Reports of Companies

The table presents data on the Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) variables and stock investment performance of five commercial banks in Nigeria from 2019 to 2023. Over the years, there is a general decline in market returns for GTBank, WEMA Bank, and UBA, while First Bank (FBN) and Access Bank exhibit fluctuating returns, with FBN showing a notable peak in 2022. The BETA coefficients, representing the market risk of the stocks, are relatively stable across the years, with minor adjustments suggesting slight changes in the sensitivity of these banks to market fluctuations. Risk-free rates, which are influenced by economic conditions, mostly hover between 9% and 12%, reflecting some volatility in economic conditions. Market capitalization, a measure of the total value of the companies' outstanding shares, remains mostly static for each bank, with a notable decrease for Access Bank in 2023, indicating a possible reduction in investor confidence or stock value. Overall, while there are yearly fluctuations in market returns and BETA values, the banks' overall

market exposure and risk-free rates reflect broader market conditions, with significant variations in stock returns linked to external economic factors.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	LOGMCAP	LOGRFR	LOGBCOEF	LOGROTM
Mean	26552497	0.106000	1.102800	1.87E+08
Median	251811.0	0.110000	1.100000	8932373.
Maximum	1.23E+08	0.120000	1.250000	1.15E+09
Minimum	115815.0	0.090000	0.950000	364598.0
Std. Dev.	49572605	0.009574	0.073173	3.24E+08
Skewness	1.483197	-1.06E-15	-0.102787	1.767437
Kurtosis	3.226320	2.078512	2.534006	5.150882
Jarque-Bera	9.219499	0.884520	0.270220	17.83502
Probability	0.009954	0.642582	0.873620	0.000134
Sum	6.64E+08	2.650000	27.57000	4.68E+09
Sum Sq. Dev.	5.90E+16	0.002200	0.128504	2.52E+18
Observations	25	25	25	25

Source: Eviews 10

The descriptive statistics in Table 2 provide a summary of the variables used in the analysis, including Market Capitalization (MCAP), Risk-Free Rate (RFR), BETA Coefficient (BCOEF), and Return on the Market (ROTM). The mean market capitalization is approximately ₦26.55 million, with a wide range between the minimum of ₦115,815 and a maximum of ₦123 million, indicating significant variation across the banks. The standard deviation of ₦49.57 million further highlights the disparity in market size among the banks. The risk-free rate (RFR) shows a stable mean of 10.6%, with a small standard deviation of 0.0096, suggesting minimal fluctuation, while the BETA coefficient has a mean of 1.10, indicating that the stocks are slightly more volatile than the market average. The BETA coefficient has a relatively low variance with a standard deviation of 0.073, meaning the market risk is fairly consistent across the banks. The return on the market (ROTM) exhibits a considerable range, with a mean of ₦187 million but a highly skewed distribution (Skewness = 1.77), indicating that a few large outliers are pulling the mean higher. The kurtosis value of 5.15 for ROTM suggests that the data distribution is leptokurtic, meaning there are extreme deviations from the mean. The Jarque-Bera statistic indicates that ROTM is not normally distributed ($p = 0.00013$), while other variables such as BCOEF and RFR show no significant departure from normality. These statistics point to substantial variability in market capitalization and returns, with more consistency in the BETA coefficient and risk-free rates across the sample of 25 observations.

Pre Test Result:

The Redundant Fixed Effects Tests help to determine whether fixed effects should be included in the panel data regression model to improve its accuracy and reliability by accounting for unobserved heterogeneity. The test compares the fixed effects model to a restricted model without fixed effects (i.e., a pooled regression model) using an F-test. If the test results indicate that the fixed effects are statistically significant (<0.05), it suggests that there are important individual-specific or time-specific factors that the fixed effects model accounts for, which the pooled regression model does not. This would imply that the fixed effects model is more appropriate for capturing the relationship between the variables under study.

Table 3: Redundant Fixed Effects Tests

Redundant Fixed Effects Tests

Equation: Untitled

Test period fixed effects

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Period F	0.258132	(4,17)	0.9007
Period Chi-square	1.474095	4	0.8312

Source: Eviews 10

The results from Table 3 of the Redundant Fixed Effects Tests indicate that neither the cross-section F-test (statistic = 0.258132, $p = 0.9007$) nor the cross-section Chi-square test (statistic = 1.474095, $p = 0.8312$) are statistically significant. These findings suggest that the inclusion of cross-sectional fixed effects does not significantly improve the model's fit. In other words, there is no strong evidence to support the hypothesis that unobserved heterogeneity across the different cross-sections (i.e., companies) has a substantial impact on the dependent variable, which is the market capitalization. Therefore, a pooled regression model, which does not include fixed effects, may be sufficient for analyzing the effect of capital asset pricing model variables (risk-free rate, beta coefficient, and return of the market) on the capitalization of commercial banks in the study. This interpretation aligns with the probability values well above the conventional significance level of 0.05, indicating that the fixed effects are redundant in this context.

Pooled Regression Model

Dependent Variable: LOG(MCAP)

Method: Panel Least Squares

Date: 10/03/24 Time: 16:46

Sample: 2019 2023

Periods included: 5

Cross-sections included: 5

Total panel (balanced) observations: 25

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-9.665389	7.181268	-1.345917	0.1927
LOG(RFR)	-4.493064	3.005177	-1.495108	0.1498
LOG(BCOEF)	-3.428014	4.102279	-0.835637	0.4128
LOG(ROTM)	0.865244	0.079488	10.88521	0.0000
R-squared	0.849879	Mean dependent var		14.20656
Adjusted R-squared	0.828433	S.D. dependent var		2.733826
S.E. of regression	1.132369	Akaike info criterion		3.232147
Sum squared resid	26.92744	Schwarz criterion		3.427167
Log likelihood	-36.40184	Hannan-Quinn criter.		3.286237
F-statistic	39.62900	Durbin-Watson stat		0.681330
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Eviews 10

Interpretation of Result

The pooled regression model examines the relationship between the logarithm of market capitalization (MCAP) and three independent variables: the logarithms of the risk-free rate (RFR), BETA coefficient (BCOEF), and return on the market (ROTM). The results show that LOG(ROTM) has a significant positive impact on LOG(MCAP), with a coefficient of 0.8652 and a highly significant p-value of 0.0000, indicating a strong positive relationship between market returns and market capitalization. However, the coefficients for LOG(RFR) and LOG(BCOEF) are negative, but neither is statistically significant with p-values of 0.1498 and 0.4128, respectively. This suggests that changes in the risk-free rate and BETA coefficient do not have a significant effect on market capitalization in this model. The R-squared value of 0.8499 indicates that 84.99% of the variation in market capitalization is explained by the model, showing a strong overall fit. The F-statistic is also highly significant ($p = 0.0000$), further supporting the model's overall significance. Overall, the model shows that market returns are a key determinant of market capitalization, while the risk-free rate and BETA coefficient have less influence.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1 (H_{01}): Risk-Free Rate (Rf) Has No Significant Impact on Market Capitalization in Nigeria

The coefficient of the risk-free rate (LOG(RFR)) is -4.4931 with a p-value of 0.1498, which is greater than the conventional significance levels of 0.05, 0.01, or 0.10. This means that the relationship between the risk-free rate and market capitalization is not statistically significant in this model. Therefore, we fail to reject the null hypothesis (H_{01}), indicating that the risk-free rate does not have a significant impact on market capitalization in Nigeria.

The negative coefficient of the risk-free rate (Rf) (-4.4931) indicates that an increase in the risk-free rate would likely lead to a decrease in market capitalization, even though the relationship is not statistically significant. This inverse relationship could imply that as risk-free rates rise (e.g., due to higher interest rates or government bond yields), investors might shift their funds away from equity investments in commercial banks toward safer, risk-free assets. However, since this result is not statistically significant (p-value = 0.1498), it suggests that the risk-free rate does not have a meaningful or consistent influence on the stock market valuations of Nigerian commercial banks. Investors in this market may not be responsive to changes in the risk-free rate when deciding whether to invest in banking stocks, potentially because they prioritize other factors, such as economic growth or bank-specific performance.

Hypothesis 2 (H_{02}): Beta Coefficient Has No Significant Impact on Market Capitalization in Nigeria

The coefficient for the BETA coefficient (LOG(BCOEF)) is -3.4280, with a p-value of 0.4128, which is also above the significance threshold of 0.05. This suggests that the BETA coefficient does not have a significant influence on market capitalization in Nigeria. Hence, we fail to reject the null hypothesis (H_{02}), confirming that the BETA coefficient does not significantly impact market capitalization in the sample.

The negative coefficient for the BETA coefficient (-3.4280) implies that an increase in systematic risk (as measured by BETA) could potentially lead to a decline in market capitalization, meaning that higher volatility relative to the market might reduce the value of bank stocks. However, this relationship is also not statistically significant (p-value = 0.4128), which means that, in this context, the risk perception of Nigerian bank stocks compared to the broader market does not have a substantial impact on their valuation. This might suggest that investors are not deterred by the relative volatility of bank stocks or that the specific risks

captured by BETA are not major factors driving stock prices in the Nigerian banking sector. The lack of significance further indicates that other factors, such as earnings or market sentiment, likely have a greater influence on market capitalization.

Hypothesis 3 (H₀₃): Return of the Market Has No Significant Impact on Market Capitalization in Nigeria

The coefficient for the return on the market (LOG(ROTM)) is 0.8652, with a highly significant p-value of 0.0000, which is below the 0.05 threshold. This implies that there is a strong and statistically significant positive relationship between market returns and market capitalization. As a result, we reject the null hypothesis (H₀₃) and conclude that the return on the market has a significant impact on market capitalization in Nigeria.

The positive coefficient of the return on the market (ROTM) (0.8652) shows that an increase in overall market returns is associated with an increase in the market capitalization of Nigerian commercial banks. The highly significant result (p-value = 0.0000) suggests that market returns are a strong and crucial factor in determining the market capitalization of these banks. The positive relationship implies that as the overall market performs well, investor confidence in bank stocks increases, driving up their market valuations. This is consistent with expectations, as positive market returns reflect a growing economy or favorable market conditions, which tend to boost stock prices. In contrast to the negative signs seen in the coefficients of the risk-free rate and BETA coefficient, the positive and significant impact of market returns highlights that general market performance is the dominant driver of market capitalization for Nigerian banks.

Discussion of Findings

The findings from the study on the Capital Asset Pricing Model and stock investment of commercial banks in Nigeria reveal that the return of the market (ROTM) plays a significant and positive role in determining the market capitalization of Nigerian banks, indicating that strong market performance drives higher stock valuations in the banking sector. The positive and statistically significant relationship between ROTM and market capitalization suggests that investors are more likely to increase their investments in bank stocks when overall market returns are favorable. In contrast, both the risk-free rate (R_f) and the BETA coefficient exhibit negative coefficients, implying that increases in these variables could potentially reduce market capitalization. However, these relationships are statistically insignificant, indicating that changes in interest rates and systematic risk (as measured by BETA) do not have a substantial impact on the market capitalization of commercial banks in Nigeria. This suggests that investors in the Nigerian banking sector prioritize overall market performance over factors like interest rates or risk when making stock investment decisions.

5.1 Summary of Findings

The study seeks to examine the impact of capital asset pricing model and stock investment decision of commercial banks in Nigeria. The coefficients with P-value were extracted from regression table using Return on market (RM), Beta Coefficient (B) and risk free rate (RFR). Stock investment decision were measured using return on marketing and market capitalization of commercial banks in Nigeria, Beta measured using market capitalization of commercial banks in Nigeria, measured using Risk free rate on market capitalization of commercial banks in Nigeria.

The findings from the empirical analysis of the study revealed the following:

1. There is positive significance impact of return on market and market capitalization. Increase in overall market returns is related with an increase in the market capitalization of Nigerian commercial banks
2. There is negative significance effect of Beta on market capitalization. increase in systematic risk (as measured by BETA) could potentially lead to a decline in market capitalization, meaning that higher volatility relative to the market might reduce the value of bank stocks.
3. There is negative significance effect of risk free rate on market capitalization. Increase in the risk-free rate would likely lead to a decrease in market capitalization

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the study concludes that market returns (ROTM) are the primary determinant of market capitalization for commercial banks in Nigeria. The positive and statistically significant relationship between ROTM and market capitalization suggests that strong market performance encourages higher stock valuations and increased investments in bank stocks. Conversely, the risk-free rate (Rf) and the BETA coefficient, which represent interest rates and systematic risk respectively, do not exhibit a statistically significant impact on market capitalization. This implies that Nigerian investors in the banking sector are more influenced by overall market performance than by interest rates or risk factors when making stock investment decisions. Therefore, for commercial banks in Nigeria, market conditions play a crucial role in shaping stock investment trends, while factors such as interest rates and risk are less influential in this context.

Recommendation

1. Banks should continuously monitor and adapt to favorable market conditions to attract more investments in their stocks
2. Banks should still seek to minimize their exposure to fluctuations in interest rates and systematic risk which could be achieved through prudent risk management practices, ensuring that any potential negative effects are mitigated.
3. Management of banks should focus on building and maintaining investor confidence by improving transparency and communication regarding market performance.

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